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CONSTANT CHANGES IN EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENTS AND THE CONTINUOUS ADVANCEMENT OF TEACHERS' MEDIA LITERACY IN THE INFORMATION AGE

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Abstract: It is important to note that in today's world, education—including media training for educators—is no longer just a phase at the start of independent life but rather an ongoing journey that individuals engage in throughout their entire lives. This indicates that the duty to prepare proficient media educators is an essential responsibility of higher education institutions. A vibrant information and educational landscape with constant changes compels educators to seek out innovative teaching methods, which is crucial for enhancing teachers' communication abilities.

Key words: media proficiency, educator, data, learning, surroundings, continuous media training, media literacy.

Annotatsiya: Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bugungi dunyoda pedagoglar uchun media-treningni o'z ichiga olgan ta'lim endi mustaqil hayotning boshlanish bosqichi emas, balki odamlar butun hayoti davomida qatnashadigan doimiy sayohatdir. Bu esa malakali media-pedagoglarni tayyorlash burchi oliy ta'lim muassasalarining muhim mas'uliyati ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Doimiy o'zgarib turadigan jonli axborot va ta'lim landshafti o'qituvchilarni innovatsion o'qitish usullarini izlashga majbur qiladi, bu esa o'qituvchilarning muloqot qobiliyatini oshirish uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: media malakasi, o'qituvchi, ma'lumotlar, o'rganish, atrof-muhit, doimiy media treningi, media savodxonligi.

Аннотация: Важно отметить, что в современном мире образование, которое включает в себя медиа-подготовку для педагогов, больше не является просто этапом в начале самостоятельной жизни, а скорее непрерывным путешествием, в которое люди вовлечены на протяжении всей своей жизни. Это указывает на то, что обязанность готовить опытных медиа-педагогов является важнейшей обязанностью высших учебных заведений. Яркий информационный и образовательный ландшафт с постоянными изменениями заставляет педагогов искать инновационные методы обучения, что имеет решающее значение для повышения коммуникативных способностей учителей.

Ключевые слова: медиа-компетентность, педагог, данные, обучение, окружение, непрерывное медиа-обучение, медиаграмотность.

INTRODUCTION

In the current dynamic social landscape, characterized by rapid changes in education and information, there is a pressing need for reforming education and adapting to evolving requirements for teachers' competencies. The concept of "lifelong education" emphasizes that the development of a teacher's media competence should be regarded as an ongoing process of media education within the framework of professional training aimed at addressing continuous challenges. At the same time, it is crucial to maintain the continuity of various forms, levels, and degrees of education: vocational training (including secondary vocational and higher education) involves providing mentoring and methodological support to novice teachers during their vocational adaptation. This includes implementing various forms of professional development for educators and organizing methodological work with teachers in schools, as well as encouraging teachers' self-education. The rapidly evolving information and instructional environments necessitate the development of media competency in educators. Teachers need to quickly recognize and understand these changes, anticipate their effects on educational practices, take the identified changes into account, plan their activities and professional identity, learn to tackle new challenges, and possess the required knowledge, skills, and abilities. In this regard, it is

essential to incorporate a new element into the framework of a teacher's media competency—the readiness to effectively address shifts in the educational and information landscape.

The aims of this article are as follows: to identify transformations in the information and educational setting that significantly impact teachers' practices and their media utilization; to support the addition of a new aspect to the framework of teachers' communication competence; to prepare for suitable reactions to alterations in the information and educational environment; to outline the structure and content of this preparation, along with the educational contexts and tools for its training, within the framework of the teacher's ongoing educational responsibilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The rapidly changing landscape of education in the digital age has made media literacy a critical competency for teachers worldwide. According to Hobbs (2010), media literacy empowers educators to critically evaluate digital content and effectively integrate it into their teaching practices. This view is supported by Kellner and Share (2007), who emphasize that media literacy should be seen not only as a technical skill but also as a means of promoting democratic participation in the classroom.

In Uzbekistan, local scholars have also begun addressing the significance of media literacy in teacher development. Karimova and Rakhimov (2022) argue that with the increasing digitization of educational environments, Uzbek teachers must continuously update their media competencies to meet the evolving needs of students. Similarly, the study by Tashkent State Pedagogical University (2023) highlights that professional development programs focusing on digital pedagogy have significantly improved teachers' confidence and engagement with ICT tools.

International studies underline the role of institutional support. For instance, Buckingham (2015) notes that while individual teacher motivation is crucial, systemic support and access to quality training are equally essential. Meanwhile, digital transformation in education systems, as described by Selwyn (2016), demands that teachers not only adapt to new technologies but also develop a critical understanding of the social implications of media use.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To accomplish the assigned tasks, a combination of analytical and design-based strategies was employed. First, an assessment of the current information and educational landscape was conducted, taking into account the ongoing transformations and their impact on teaching activities, teacher-student interactions, and the use of media. This diagnostic stage helped to determine how such shifts affect the daily professional responsibilities of educators. Next, the structure and content of teacher training were formulated to address the identified changes effectively, with particular emphasis on enhancing communication skills and media competence. Furthermore, a simulation approach was applied to envision the integration of this training within the broader framework of ongoing media education. These strategies were implemented in alignment with the methodological principles rooted in the theory of media education and the continuous development of teachers' media competencies, ensuring both theoretical grounding and practical relevance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A significant amount of research is being carried out globally on media education, the integration of media into the educational process, and enhancing teachers' media skills in the current information society. These studies illustrate the essence of media education, its capabilities, educational potential, and the conditions for using various educational resources (such as information technology, the Internet, social networks, and art), along with the models and tools necessary to prepare and equip educators to use them (e.g., screen arts, reading, television, advertising, interactive games, and computer animation). Nevertheless, fundamental aspects of communication competency—such as instructors' willingness to fully adapt to the ongoing transformations within the educational landscape—have received limited attention in previous studies. Essential elements include gathering information, assessing and predicting changes, improving personal attributes and skills, and acquiring new knowledge and relevant competencies.

At the same time, transformations in the educational and information environments are occurring due to reforms in education, advances in information technology, and the growing diversity of information types and sources. The investigation revealed several significant changes in the information environment that strongly impact elements of teachers' media competence: an increase in the volume of transmitted data and the models used for its processing; distribution of software that may be influenced by the average user; advancement of

human-machine interfaces, artificial intelligence technologies, semantic systems that process the meanings of natural language, and neural interfaces; the emergence of quantum and optical computing, among others. The educational landscape responds differently to shifts in the information environment: unique training tools are being implemented through information technologies; network-based approaches for delivering educational programs are being developed; remote technologies, such as e-learning, are becoming widespread; robotics courses are being integrated into school curricula; various methods are being tested to immerse students into productive states of consciousness during training through the use of information technologies (e.g., the flow state, where an individual becomes completely absorbed in the creative process without experiencing anxiety).

The following principles form the conceptual basis for crafting the model and may also be regarded as conditions necessary for building a teacher's readiness to adapt effectively to the transformations in information and educational environments:

1. Utilizing games that leverage social networks, information and communication technologies, e-learning platforms, distance learning tools, electronic library systems, databases, topic-oriented websites, Internet forums, online surveys, and modern research software—including industry-standard analytical tools—as well as implementing a point-rating evaluation system via electronic platforms.
2. In their professional roles within schools or specialized organizations, teachers employ media to fulfill a variety of tasks: maintaining databases to track student achievements, automating activity management, preparing thematic and educational plans electronically, managing students' journals and diaries, and actively using interactive whiteboards.
3. Educators should utilize media as a means to achieve educational and training objectives, not as an end in itself. The success of media in supporting teaching depends significantly on the professional competencies of the teacher.
4. In developing pedagogical interactions involving media, emphasis should be placed on both the teacher and the students, with media serving as a tool to enhance engagement—especially in light of evolving educational and informational landscapes.
5. Teachers should not only possess the skills to use media, but also to create it in order to address educational and instructional challenges.
6. Media should be emphasized as a motivational tool that fosters teachers' interest in social, professional, and personally meaningful topics.

Consequently, educators must be proficient in techniques that inspire students to achieve educational, social, and personal goals through media. It is essential for teachers to cultivate both knowledge and resilience—in themselves and their students—against the negative impacts of media on spiritual and moral development. While using media to address educational goals, teachers should maintain creative originality, a distinct professional perspective, and effective pedagogical communication. Furthermore, they should strive to select media resources that reflect high cultural and intellectual standards.

Maintaining an effective balance between individual, group, and collective work methods is critical in developing a teacher's readiness to respond to shifts in the information and educational environment. This includes providing personalized support to overcome barriers in implementing pedagogical innovations, offering tutor guidance for designing and executing media competence programs, organizing group psychological and pedagogical training, and engaging in collaborative design projects.

Ensuring the continuity of media education is vital. Teachers must be equipped to respond to evolving information and educational landscapes while maintaining consistency in content and methods across all levels and stages of education and self-development.

CONCLUSIONS

Consequently, the following conclusions can be drawn: creating an environment in which instructors are fully prepared to embrace changes in the information and educational landscape should be fostered through problem-solving approaches in the classroom. Ongoing communication and continuous education for instructors ensure alignment of objectives and content across various levels: professional education (both vocational secondary and higher education); mentorship and methodological support for novice teachers during their career adaptation phase; integration of AI into teacher development strategies; implementation of diverse approaches to professional development; establishment of a structured system for working with teachers at schools; promotion of instructors' own pursuit of lifelong learning.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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